

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers:

Here is the May issue of vol.4 of J.UCS with five very interesting papers: I am sure you will enjoy reading them.

I would like to take this opportunity to thank all contributors, editors, guest editors of special issues, all readers, Springer Heidelberg, all the support staff, and my co-editors-in-chief for helping make J.UCS what it is. Please keep supporting J.UCS!

I am happy to be able to report that our efforts show strong signs of success: J.UCS will continue to grow with your help into a major publication. In a recent meeting with Springer Heidelberg it was decided that J.UCS volumes 1 - 4 (i.e. 1995 - 1998) would remain free of charge on our server in Graz (<http://www.iicm.edu/jucs>), that the volumes 1 - 6 (i.e. 1995 - 2000) will be made available for any institution that runs a WWW server of type Hyperwave for a total of only US \$ 200.- (and for US \$ 100.- per year, afterwards). I feel that 6 years of a high-quality journal for two hundred dollars is quite a deal, and I hope that many of you will make use of this forthcoming offer. The WWW server Hyperwave (<http://www.hyperwave.com>) is free of charge for universities; and a growing number of other big organisations are running Hyperwave, anyway. For those who don't want to run Hyperwave, a "DLP" (Digital Library Plugin) based on Hyperwave for other servers is in the planning stage. J.UCS will also be available for a yearly subscription fee of US \$100.- on Springer's LINK server starting in 1999 (<http://link.springer.de> or <http://link.springer-ny.com>). B.T.W., abstracts of the papers in J.UCS are already available freely on that server right now. Also, Springer will continue to publish an archive edition (printed version of J.UCS plus CD-ROM). Note that the nice archive editions for both 1995 and 1996 have appeared and can be ordered like any other book (for a price of DM 298.-). Members of the Editorial Board of J.UCS enjoy a special rate of DM 120.- if they order the volume directly through Dr. H. Woessner at woessner@springer.de . In 1999, the amount of interactivity available within J.UCS will be once more increased and more widely advertised: after all, J.UCS is the only big electronic journal that allows group- and private annotations and links, yet few readers seem to be even aware of this feature. Have you tried them out?

All counted, we have come a long way since the pilot issue in 1994. Due to the number of papers to be reviewed we are planning to expand our editorial board further: if you are interested in actively participating in J.UCS, willing to review some 2 - 4 papers per year, willing to encourage persons to submit high quality manuscripts once in a while (including some of your own?), and if you are recognized in your field as leading scientist, please let me know: send your areas of expertise and your CV to hmaurer@iicm.edu. The editors-in-chief will then determine if in your areas of expertise further help is needed. Note that it is intended to keep the editorial-board of J.UCS balanced in every way including geographic location and scientific area.

Enough for now,

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
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